

A Mathematical Model to Identify the Occurrence of Stuck Bits in Radiation-Ground Test

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Abstract

This manuscript presents a mathematical model to estimate the expected number of flipped cells that appear in two different rounds of reading in radiation tests exclusively related to single-event upsets in memories and that the occurrences must be attributed to randomness. This model only requires the number of bitflips per round and the size of the memory, and it is independent of the multiplicity of the upsets. Deviations from the theoretical predictions of the model are clues to determine if there are persistent errors in the memory, such as stuck bits. The model is validated by means of Monte Carlo calculations and with data from actual radiation experiments.

Index Terms

Neutrons, single events, SRAM, stuck bits.

I. INTRODUCTION

STATISTICAL properties of radiation data sets have become a valuable tool for researchers to understand the characteristics of the irradiated devices and the reliability of the data. Thus, they are necessary to correctly plan the tests [1], and it is possible to know how likely false Multiple Cell Upsets (MCUs) are due to the accumulation of bitflips [2], [3] or even calculate their expected number [4], [5]. Statistical properties are useful to classify events into Single Bit Upsets (SBUs) and MCUs despite the lack of knowledge about the internal structure of the device and they have been successfully used in radiation-ground experiments with Static Random Access Memories (SRAMs) [6]–[8] and Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) [9]–[13].

Another field of interest is the ability to distinguish Single Event Upsets (SEUs) from other Single Event Effects (SEEs). For example, statistical properties have been used to clean data sets issued from pseudo-static tests of Single Event Functional Interrupts (SEFIs), keeping only bitflips originating in SEUs [14]. A pseudo-static test consists of the periodic reading of a memory written with a known pattern. When not accessed, the memory is in standby mode, unlike dynamic tests, in which the memory is in a nonstop reading and writing cycle while the irradiation is performed [15].

Stuck bits are a phenomenon observed in different types of memories, especially Dynamic Random Access Memories (DRAMs). The exact mechanism that leads to this phenomenon is still under research. It has been claimed that it occurs due to microdose effects following the impact of a particle, after which the cell stores a permanent value and cannot be written any longer, at least until annealing allows the recovery of the device [16], [17]. However, other mechanisms have been proposed, such as single-ion displacement damage [18]–[22], or just total ionizing dose (TID) combined with variation of internal parameters of the memory [23]–[25]. More recent works support the theory of the microdose effects [26]–[28].

It may seem easy to detect the occurrence of stuck bits in pseudo-static and dynamic tests, but in some situations, it is not so. For example, if the stuck bit quickly disappears after the particle hit due to annealing and is observed in only some rounds, or perhaps if the device is destroyed by a Single Event Latchup (SEL) and cannot be tested offline. This paper presents a mathematical model that allows calculating the probability of observing bitflips in the same cell in tests done in different reading and writing rounds (pseudo-static or dynamic) and that provides objective evidence to distinguish stuck bits from bitflips.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Let us suppose that a memory of L bits has been irradiated in N_R rounds, observing N_i bitflips in the i^{th} round, with $1 \leq i \leq N_R$.

There have been N_T bitflips in total, and it is immediate that the total number of bitflips, N_T , is

$$N_T = \sum_{i=1}^{N_R} N_i. \quad (1)$$

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For the sake of simplicity, let us accept that only SBUs occur. Now, let us focus on one of the N_T successful particles that hit the memory and provoked a bitflip. If all the cells have identical cross section for events of any multiplicity during the full duration of the test, or at least with a very narrow scattering around the average values, the probability of a specific cell of the memory flipping as a consequence of this specific impact is just

$$r = 1/L, \quad (2)$$

and the probability of not being flipped in this specific particle impact is

$$1 - r. \quad (3)$$

It is quite easy to deduce using the Theory of Probability that the probability of a specific cell not being flipped during the whole radiation test is just the product of probabilities of that specific cell not having been flipped by any of the N_T successful particles:

$$P(0) = (1 - r)^{N_T}. \quad (4)$$

As there are L cells in the memory, the expected number of cells not flipped is

$$N_{CF}(0) = L \cdot P(0) = L \cdot (1 - r)^{N_T}, \quad (5)$$

in which the “CF” subindex reads “cell flips”. In general, $N_{CF}(k)$ means “the number of cells flipped in k independent rounds”. As one can see, $N_{CF}(0)$ does not depend on the number of reading rounds, N_R , or in the specific number of bitflips in any of them.

The number of cells expected to be flipped only once in the entire experiment, $N_{CF}(1)$, can also be easily calculated with the following statement. In this case, the cell was flipped by one of the N_T successful particles and not flipped by any of the remaining $N_T - 1$ ones. The probability of this is

$$r \cdot (1 - r)^{N_T - 1}, \quad (6)$$

but, as the very same phenomenon occurs N_T times, for each one of the N_T bitflips, the probability of Eq. 6 must be multiplied by N_T . Therefore,

$$P(1) = N_T \cdot r \cdot (1 - r)^{N_T - 1}, \quad (7)$$

and the expected number of cells flipped only once is

$$N_{CF}(1) = L \cdot P(1) = N_T \cdot (1 - r)^{N_T - 1}. \quad (8)$$

As in the previous case, $N_{CF}(1)$ is independent of how the bitflips are distributed within the reading rounds. However, this dependence on only global parameters disappears for cells that are hit in two or more rounds. Let us calculate the probability of a cell being hit in rounds i & j . In the former, N_i cells were flipped, N_j in the latter. Additionally, the involved cell must not be hit in the other $N_R - 2$ rounds. The probability of this cell being hit in the i^{th} round is

$$N_i \cdot r \cdot (1 - r)^{N_i - 1},$$

which is equivalent to (7) just restricting the number of bitflips to this specific round (N_i instead of to the total number of bitflips, N_T). Regarding the j^{th} round:

$$N_j \cdot r \cdot (1 - r)^{N_j - 1}.$$

The cell must not be hit in the rest of the rounds, and the associated probability is

$$(1 - r)^{N_1} \cdot (1 - r)^{N_2} \cdot \dots \cdot (1 - r)^{N_{i-1}} \cdot (1 - r)^{N_{i+1}} \cdot \dots \\ \cdot (1 - r)^{N_{j-1}} \cdot (1 - r)^{N_{j+1}} \cdot \dots \cdot (1 - r)^{N_{N_R}}$$

The probability of one cell being hit in rounds i^{th} & j^{th} is calculated by the product of the three former expressions. After an elementary handling of this huge mathematical expression, the following probability arises:

$$N_i \cdot N_j \cdot r^2 \cdot (1 - r)^{N_T - 2}$$

However, this can occur in all the possible pairs of rounds i & j . Therefore, the probability of any cell being hit in two different rounds is the sum of all the combinations:

$$P(2) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_R - 1} \sum_{j=i+1}^{N_R} N_i \cdot N_j \cdot r^2 \cdot (1 - r)^{N_T - 2} \quad (9)$$

The nested sums cover all the possible combinations of i & j . The expected number of cells appearing in two rounds is

$$\begin{aligned}
N_{CF}(2) &= L \cdot P(2) = \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^{N_R-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^{N_R} N_i \cdot N_j \cdot r \cdot (1-r)^{N_T-2}.
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

The reasoning can be extended to values higher than 2, obtaining expressions with more and more nested sums but with similar cores. To summarize, let us define beforehand a function, $S(q)$, as

$$S(q) = \sum_{C_q} \underbrace{N_i \cdot N_j \cdot \dots}_{q \text{ factors}}, \tag{11}$$

C_q being the set of all the possible combinations without repetition of q values of N_i among the total N_R ones. Some values are immediately deducible. For example:

$$\begin{aligned}
S(1) &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_R} N_i = N_T, \\
S(N_R) &= \prod_{i=1}^{N_R} N_i,
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$S(q) = 0, \quad q > N_R.$$

On the contrary, the expressions for values of q such that $2 < q < N_R$ become more and more complex:

$$\begin{aligned}
S(2) &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_R-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^{N_R} N_i \cdot N_j, \\
S(3) &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_R-2} \sum_{j=i+1}^{N_R-1} \sum_{k=j+1}^{N_R} N_i \cdot N_j \cdot N_k.
\end{aligned}$$

Finally, let us postulate that $S(0) = 1$ for completeness. One can notice the presence of $S(0)$, $S(1)$ and $S(2)$ in (5), (8) and (10) respectively. Taking these expressions into account, it is possible to deduce that the expected number of cells flipped q times due to single-bit upsets during the experiment is

$$N_{CF}(q) = S(q) \cdot r^{q-1} \cdot (1-r)^{N_T-q}. \tag{12}$$

A deeper study can be performed to deduce what happens if m -multiplicity MCUs occur instead of SBUs. The number of events per round would be N_i/m , the total number of hits N_T/m and r should be recalculated as m/L . Thus, with all these new concepts, the following expression would appear:

$$N_{CF}(q) = S(q) \cdot r^{q-1} \cdot (1-m \cdot r)^{\frac{N_T}{m}-q}. \tag{13}$$

Given that $m \cdot r \ll 1$, $(1-m \cdot r)^{\frac{N_T}{m}-q} \approx 1 - (N_T - q \cdot m) \cdot r$ so the influence of the multiplicity is negligible if $(N_T - q \cdot m)/L \ll 1$, which is equivalent to get much more bitflips per round than the maximum multiplicity. A consequence of this is that the results in actual experiments, where there are events of several multiplicities would be hardly different from the model with only SBUs.

$S(q)$ can be calculated using a program with nested loops, which can lead to a high computation load. An approximate expression may be taken from (11) supposing that the number of bitflips per round is constant and equal to N_T/N_R . In this case, the factors inside the nested sums of (11) are approximated as

$$N_i \cdot N_j \cdot \dots \rightarrow \left(\frac{N_T}{N_R}\right)^q$$

and the function $S(q)$ as

$$S(q) = \sum_{C_q} \underbrace{N_i \cdot N_j \cdot \dots}_{q \text{ factors}} \approx \left(\frac{N_T}{N_R}\right)^q \cdot N_{C_q},$$

where N_{C_q} is the number of combinations of q elements of natural numbers between 1 and N_R . However, this value is obtained through the binomial yielding an alternative expression of $S(q)$, $S^*(q)$, such that:

$$S^*(q) \approx \left(\frac{N_T}{N_R}\right)^q \cdot \binom{N_R}{q}. \tag{14}$$

For $q = 0$ and $q = 1$, $S^*(q)$ coincides with $S(q)$. It is important to take into account that the equivalence between $S(q)$ and $S^*(q)$ has only been proposed, and not demonstrated. It is immediate that the closer the values of N_i, N_j, \dots to the average value, N_T/N_R , the better the identification of the formulae. This is especially important if events of very large size can occur, since the occurrence of only one event of this size can significantly deviate the number of bitflips in that round from the average value.

III. MONTE CARLO SIMULATIONS

The correctness of Eq. 12, either using Eq. 11 or 14, was validated through a synthetic experiment consisting of Monte Carlo simulations. For this purpose, it was supposed that the memory was similar to the 130-nm device studied at [6], with SEE cross-sections ranging from $1.75 \cdot 10^{-15}$ cm²/bit for SBUs to $6.4 \cdot 10^{-17}$ cm²/bit for 7-bit MCUs (Table I). The memory size was assumed to be $2^{20} = 1,048,576$ bits to gather significant results in a finite time. The simulated particle fluence per round was set to $1.6 \cdot 10^{10}$ cm⁻² to generate around 65 bitflips per round.

TABLE I
PER-BIT SBU/MCU CROSS-SECTIONS USED IN THE MONTE CARLO SIMULATIONS TO VALIDATE THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL PRESENTED IN THIS PAPER.

SEU Multiplicity	Cross section
1	17.5
2	2.6
3-7	0.65
> 7	0
	$\times 10^{-16}$ cm ⁻²

The emulated experiment consisted of 100 rounds and, in every round, the numbers of events of each type (i.e., SBUs and MCUs with different multiplicities) were randomly chosen using Poisson distributions whose λ 's were derived from the cross sections, memory size, and particle fluence discussed in the previous paragraph. After every round, the flipped addresses were saved in a histogram, and after completing the 100 rounds, the program counted the addresses that had appeared 0, 1, 2, or 3 times or more. This experiment was run 1,000 times to get a reasonable estimate of these values.

In these conditions, it was observed that some cells were randomly hit in 1, 2, or even 3 rounds in some of the trials. Table II shows the mean number of cells flipped q times in the Monte Carlo experiment, as well as the predictions made by Eq. 12 in combination with Eqs. 11 or 14. One can see that both predictions quite accurately match the results of the Monte Carlo test, and that the difference between the accurate and the simplified models is negligible.

TABLE II
VALUES FOR $N_{CF}(q)$ FOR DIFFERENT VALUES OF q , OBTAINED IN A SYNTHETIC EXPERIMENT WITH MONTE CARLO SIMULATIONS AND PREDICTIONS ISSUED FROM EQ. 12, USING EITHER $S(q)$ (EQ. 11) OR $S^*(q)$ (EQ. 14).

Occurrences (q)	Monte Carlo	Accurate Eqs. 12 & 11	Simplified Eqs. 12 & 14
0	1,042,175.1±0.3	1,042,174.6	
1	6,381.31±0.66	6,381.81	
2	19.58±0.333	19.335	19.344
3	0.056±0.038	0.0386	0.0387
4	0	$5.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$

IV. APPLICATION TO ACTUAL RADIATION DATA SETS

A. Decision criteria

Once the value of $N_{CF}(q)$ has been correctly estimated in the previous section, it is possible to establish a criterion to decide whether a cell appearing several times is a stuck bit or not.

Let us remember that this model is applied to a radiation-ground experiment on a memory with L bits, doing N_R reading rounds where N_T bitflips were observed in total. The model allows calculating $N_{CF}(q)$ for any possible q . Next, $N_{CF}(q)$ can be used with a criterion similar to that used in [14]. The researcher chooses a threshold value, ε , such that $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$, and any value of q that makes

$$N_{CF}(q) < \varepsilon \quad (15)$$

is immediately ruled out. Given that, in practice, $S(q) \approx S^*(q)$, $S^*(q)$ will be used in the rest of the paper since it is much easier to calculate. Concerning ε , the authors of [14] propose 10^{-10} . However, as this paper works with probabilities instead of the expected number of occurrences, this threshold should not be directly used, but it must be multiplied by L to transform that threshold (which is a probability value) into another value in terms of expected number of occurrences.

The other strategy consists of defining a p -value test. Let $N_{CF,EXP}(q)$ be the number of cells that flipped q times in the experiment, and q_{MAX} the highest possible value of q in the experiment. The χ_{EXP}^2 -value associated with this set of data and model is:

$$\chi_{EXP}^2 = \sum_{q=0}^{q_{MAX}+1} \frac{(N_{CF}(q) - N_{CF,EXP}(q))^2}{N_{CF}(q)}. \quad (16)$$

In this expression, the $(q_{MAX} + 1)^{th}$ -term has been included to explicitly state that no cells are flipped more than q_{MAX} times in the experiment. The related p -value is:

$$p = 1 - \chi_{CMF}^2(\chi_{EXP}^2, \nu). \quad (17)$$

χ_{CMF}^2 is the cumulative mass function for the well-known χ^2 -distribution, and ν is the number of degrees of freedom. Given that the number of addends in Eq. 16 is

$$q_{MAX} + 2,$$

but the sum of all the values of $N_{CF}(q)$ is exactly L , there exists a unique constraint reducing the number of degrees of freedom so

$$\nu = q_{MAX} + 1.$$

Next, as it is done in plenty of science fields, if $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis (i.e., no stuck bits occurred, so $N_{CF,EXP}(q)$ is depicted by Eq. 12)) must be rejected, so it is postulated that other phenomena such as stuck bits must have occurred.

B. Radiation experiments

To illustrate the application of the criteria explained in the previous subsection, we will utilize data from radiation-ground experiments conducted on various SRAMs, including both classical and additional features, at ENEA [29] in two campaigns performed in 2023 and 2025. The memories were irradiated with 14-MeV neutrons in different rounds.

1) *Classical Bulk CMOS SRAMs*: The typical cell of this family of devices is built using the well-known 6-transistor structure, and stuck bits are quite unusual [26].

First of all, the IS61WV204816BLL-10TLI, a 32-Mbit 40-nm bulk CMOS SRAM by ISSI ($L = 2^{25}$ bits) was tested in 61 rounds receiving a fluence of around $3.2 \cdot 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ per round, $1.96 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in total. This generated 60,604 bitflips (~ 994 bitflips per round). In one of the rounds the number of bitflips was anomalously high (5251), probably associated with some sort of SEFI that affected several blocks of 32 16-bit words with addresses starting in 0×000000 , 0×008000 , 0×010000 , 0×018000 , 0×020000 , 0×030000 , etc. Table III shows the number of cells flipped q times (for $0 \leq q \leq 3$), indicating that, for instance, 68 cells were flipped in 2 different rounds. However, the statistical analysis shows that these repetitions may have occurred by chance and that the data set is compatible with a scenario with only SEUs. Accepting the criterion of Eq. 15 with $\varepsilon = 10^{-10} \cdot L \approx 0.03$, Eqs. 12 and 14 predict that, at least, 4 or more occurrences are necessary to conclude that phenomena other than SEUs have taken place. Besides, the calculated p -value (0.469) is consistent with the case of only occurring SEUs. Bulk CMOS SRAMs are quite insensitive to stuck bits [26], so the experimental results are consistent with the expected ones.

TABLE III
VALUES FOR $N_{EXP,CF}(q)$ AND $N_{CF}(q)$ (EQS. 12 & 14), FOR AN EXPERIMENT CARRIED OUT ON A 40-NM BULK CMOS SRAM BY ISSI.
SEE EQS. 16 AND 17 FOR DEFINITIONS OF χ_{EXP}^2 AND p .

Occurrences (q)	Observed $N_{EXP,CF}(q)$	Expected $N_{CF}(q)$
0	33,493,896	33,493,882.7
1	60,468	60,494.6
2	68	53.74
3	0	0.031

$$\chi_{EXP}^2 = 3.83 \quad p = 0.469 > 0.05$$

To complete the information about this experiment, it is worth mentioning that they were analyzed in another work using the LELAPE toolbox [30], which could determine the number of occurrences of different SEUs (Table IV) by means of other statistical properties of the dataset. The anomalous round with a SEFI was excluded following the criterion by Perez-Celis [14].

TABLE IV
NUMBER OF ESTIMATED SBUS & MCUS FOR THE 40-NM SRAM UNDER 14-MeV NEUTRONS AT 3.3V WITH 0×5555 PATTERN.

Multiplicity	Occurrences	Multiplicity	Occurrences
1	35651	9	4
2	7195	10	1
3	1089	11	1
4	288	12	3
5	74	14	3
6	34	16	1
7	7	23	1
8	12	Other	0

Memory size: 33,554,432 Fluence: $1.93 \cdot 10^{11} \text{cm}^{-2}$

Another typical bulk CMOS SRAM is the 16-Mbit 90-nm CY62167E by Infineon ($L = 2^{24}$ bits). In this case, there were 60 rounds with a fluence of $8 \cdot 10^8 \text{cm}^{-2}$ each, gathering 17,663 bitflips. According to the criterion from Eq. (15), no cell should appear 4 times or more since $N_{CF}(4) = 7.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$, much lower than $\varepsilon \cdot L = 0.0016$. Even more, three occurrences, with an expected number equal to 0.0031, are not ruled out but are quite unusual. Table V summarizes the results for this memory, showing that the experiment also passes the p -test. Also, as in the previous case, Table VI shows the total number of SBUS & MCUS.

TABLE V
VALUES FOR $N_{\text{EXP},CF}(q)$ AND $N_{CF}(q)$ (EQS. 12 & 14), FOR AN EXPERIMENT CARRIED OUT ON A 90-NM BULK CMOS SRAM BY INFINEON. SEE EQS. 16 AND 17 FOR DEFINITIONS OF χ_{EXP}^2 AND p .

Occurrences (q)	Observed $N_{\text{EXP},CF}(q)$	Expected $N_{CF}(q)$
0	16,759,564	16,759,562.29
1	17,641	17,644.42
2	11	9.13
3	0	0.030

$\chi_{\text{EXP}}^2 = 0.39$ $p = 0.976 > 0.05$

TABLE VI
NUMBER OF ESTIMATED SBUS & MCUS FOR THE 90-NM SRAM UNDER 14-MeV NEUTRONS AT 3.3V WITH 0×5555 PATTERN.

Multiplicity	Occurrences	Multiplicity	Occurrences
1	14710	6	8
2	1059	7	6
3	139	8	4
4	57	9	2
5	10	Other	0

Memory size: 16,777,216 Fluence: $4.8 \cdot 10^{10} \text{cm}^{-2}$

2) *Other memories*: The 16-Mbit RMLV1616AGSA-5S2 Advanced Low-Power SRAM (A-LPSRAM), manufactured by Renesas in 110-nm technology ($L = 2^{24}$ bits), was tested in the same test campaign. In this case, the cells are built using the classical 6-transistor structure, but additional capacitors are added to achieve improved tolerance to SEUs. However, it was observed that this modification made the devices prone to suffer the so-called “*low voltage stuck bits*” [31]. Due to the trap of charge in the capacitors, the minimum bias voltage needed to keep the information increases so, if the SRAM bias voltage goes down during stand-by near the minimum bias voltage, the cell is erased and changes to its natural state, 0 or 1, which can be different from the original value.

In this test, the device was filled with the $0px \times px5555$ pattern and exposed to 8 rounds of neutron radiation during which the bias voltage dropped down to values between 750 and 1,010 mV. The fluence ranged from $8 \cdot 10^8$ and $4.46 \cdot 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$, the accumulated neutron fluence being $2.3 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, and 62 bitflips were observed in total. Some of them appeared twice or more, as Table VII shows. As expected, the set of data is impossible to depict with the only-SEU model, so other phenomena such as stuck bits have occurred. The criterion given by Eq. 15 indicates that no cell can be flipped 2 times or more, since

$$N_{CF}(2) = 0.0001 < 10^{-10} \cdot L \approx 1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}.$$

Hence, all the cells appearing twice or more do not originate in SEUs. Two factors support this idea. First of all, these errors remained even after the irradiation test concluded, and were observed just by lowering the bias voltage after each round with the beam off. Also, the number went up due to the accumulation of these events, a typical behavior of stuck bits. Results performed in Pseudo SRAMs, which are a subfamily of DRAMs, and presented in the remainder of this section, are equivalent to these.

TABLE VII
VALUES FOR $N_{EXP,CF}(q)$ AND $N_{CF}(q)$ (EQS. 12 & 14), FOR AN EXPERIMENT CARRIED OUT ON A 110-NM ADVANCED LOW-POWER CMOS SRAM. SEE EQS. 16 AND 17 FOR DEFINITIONS OF χ_{EXP}^2 AND p .

Occurrences (q)	Observed $N_{EXP,CF}(q)$	Expected $N_{CF}(q)$
0	16,777,183	16,777,154.0
1	11	62.0
2	18	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$
3	2	$9.3 \cdot 10^{-11}$
4	1	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-17}$
5	1	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-23}$
6	0	$4.6 \cdot 10^{-30}$

$$\chi_{EXP}^2 = 5.06 \cdot 10^{22} \quad p = 0.00 < 0.05$$

Other interesting results were obtained from the APS1604L-3SQR (manufactured by AP MemoryTechnology). This is a 16-Mbit Pseudo SRAM with SPI interface. This device is indeed a dynamic random access memory with an internal interface and refresh system so that it can be similar to an SRAM from the user's point of view.

Dynamic tests (March C & Dynamic Stress [15]) with different frequencies were performed while the sample was exposed to neutron radiation. Very few errors were observed, the origin of most of which were SEFIs, as it was reported in a previous work [32]. In total, there were 29 reading rounds (9 March-C at 4 MHz, 13 at 12-MHz, 7 Dynamic Stress at 4 MHz), receiving the March-C test rounds 10^{12} cm^{-2} each in 10 minutes, and the Dynamic Stress ones $1.9 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in 25 minutes each. The system registered 865 bitflips, of which 818 occurred on a unique round, a clear mark of a SEFI. However, the mathematical model does not care about the origin of the bitflips if they can be fixed just by writing the cell with the correct value, and dynamic and pseudostatic tests are indistinguishable from a mathematical point of view. Even more, both the kind of test and frequency do not matter, and the only key point is that the sample was not replaced during the irradiation.

The strong asymmetry in the distribution of events per round challenges the predictions of the model. Table VIII shows the number of rounds with the corresponding number of bitflips. On average, there were 50.9 bitflips per round. Table IX shows some of the calculated values for $S(q)$ & $S^*(q)$ in these conditions. Clearly, the approximation overestimates the actual value in case of asymmetry.

TABLE VIII
NUMBER OF ROUNDS PER NUMBER OF BITFLIPS FOR THE APS1604L-3SQR (17 ROUNDS, 865 BITFLIPS).

Bitflips	Rounds	Bitflips	Rounds	Bitflips	Rounds
1	4	3	3	8	1
2	3	4	5	818	1

TABLE IX
ESTIMATED VALUES OF THE $S(q)$ -FUNCTION FOR THE APS1604L-3SQR.

q	$S(q)$	$S^*(q)$
0	1	1
1	865	865
2	33,738	352,105
3	617,180	$8.96 \cdot 10^7$
4	6,936,578	$1.59 \cdot 10^{10}$

However, it is better to go on using $S^*(q)$ instead of $S(q)$ for simplicity. Using this expression, it is predicted that $N_{CF}(2) \approx 0.0215$, above the threshold level of Eq. 15 ($\varepsilon \cdot L = 0.0016$), so the accidental double occurrence of a cell is feasible although unlikely. This does not change if $S(q)$ is used instead of $S^*(q)$, since the predicted value is 0.002. In both cases, three repetitions or more are unlikely. Table X shows that one cell appeared 9 times, well above the predictions. In fact, 6 cells were stuck at some value and were easily recognizable at a glance. This seems to slightly contradict what is stated in [32], where only 5 stuck cells were observed. The reason is that, in that paper, stuck bits were sought in the files issued from one of the three performed tests, and in the present work, the experiments have been considered as a whole for mathematical purposes.

TABLE X
VALUES FOR $N_{EXP,CF}(q)$ AND $N_{CF}(q)$ (EQS. 12 & 14), FOR AN EXPERIMENT CARRIED OUT ON A SERIAL PSRAM. SEE EQS. 16 AND 17 FOR DEFINITIONS OF χ_{EXP}^2 AND p .

Occurrences (q)	Observed $N_{EXP,CF}(q)$	Expected $N_{CF}(q)$
0	16,776,384	16,776,351.0
1	825	864.96
2	1	$2.15 \cdot 10^{-2}$
3	1	$3.4 \cdot 10^{-7}$
4	0	$4.0 \cdot 10^{-12}$
5	1	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-17}$
6	1	0.0
7	1	0.0
8	1	0.0
9	1	0.0
10	0	0.0

$$\chi_{EXP}^2 = 3.3 \cdot 10^{37} \quad p = 0.00 < 0.05$$

V. DISCUSSION

The mathematical model presented in Section II has provided quite simple equations that accurately predict the number of times the cells flipped by radiation should be repeated in a scenario where no stuck bits occur, in a pseudo-static or dynamic experiment consisting of several rounds. Its main achievement consists of providing researchers with an objective criterion to decide with statistical validity if there is something else than SEUs in the data set, thus avoiding making decisions based on subjective impressions.

This model was initially developed to distinguish SEUs from stuck bits. However, the model relies on the fact that the probability of a cell being flipped is constant for all the cells and that the overlaying of stuck bits, which may inevitably appear

during the experiment, is easy to identify. However, any other phenomena leading to a significant increase in the probability of flipping can be detected as well. Thus, in some kinds of SEFIs, an anomalous increase in the cross-section of individual cells would lead to a statistical test failure, and another complementary study should be mandatory. For example, SEFIs would lead to significant clusters of repeated addresses, cells with increased cross-section could not appear in all the rounds after the first occurrence, etc.

Finally, this method has been proposed to study the results of pseudo-static and dynamic tests. This is straightforward since in both cases there are several rounds of reading. However, the mathematical model does not require that the data be collected this way. According to the presumptions in Section II, it is only necessary to have several rounds with bitflips. There is no condition about the bias voltage, the temperature, the angle of incidence, etc., so the test can be applied even to irradiation rounds in static mode, in which some of the mentioned parameters are changed. For instance, data from the A-LPSRAM shown in Section IV-B were obtained from dynamic voltage scaling tests at different bias voltage values. It is necessary to pay attention to the written pattern, as the following simple example shows. If only two irradiation rounds in static mode are performed, one with an all-one pattern and the other with an all-zero, it is completely impossible to know if there are stuck bits or not. Besides, the results cannot be extrapolated from sample to sample of the same model.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A mathematical model is proposed to accurately determine the expected number of cells that can appear twice or more in different irradiation rounds of a specific sample of a memory (SRAM, DRAM, FPGA, ...). This model only needs as input the memory size in bits, the total number of bitflips, and the number of reading rounds. Deviations from this model can be used to determine if a bitflip comes from SEUs or stuck bits with rigorous criteria. The model is supported by Monte Carlo simulations and experimental results in different memories.

OPEN DATA REPOSITORY

All the experimental data, as well as the files for treatment and the source file for Monte Carlo calculations, are freely available on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18909380>.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Quinn and G. Tompkins, "Measuring Zero: Neutron Testing of Modern Digital Electronics," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 71, pp. 670–679, Apr. 2024. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2024.3359572.
- [2] P. Reviriego and J. A. Maestro, "A technique to calculate the MBU distribution of a memory under radiation suffering the event accumulation problem," in *RADECS2008. European Conference on Radiation and Its Effects on Components and Systems*, pp. 393–396, IEEE, Sept. 2008. doi: 10.1109/RADECS.2008.5782750.
- [3] H. J. Tausch, "Simplified Birthday Statistics and Hamming EDAC," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 56, no. 2, pp. 474–478, Apr. 2009. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2009.2012710.
- [4] F. J. Franco, J. A. Clemente, H. Mecha, and R. Velazco, "Influence of Randomness During the Interpretation of Results From Single-Event Experiments on SRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Device Mater. Reliab.*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 104–111, Mar. 2019. doi: 10.1109/TDMR.2018.2886358.
- [5] F. J. Franco, J. A. Clemente, G. Korkian, J. C. Fabero, H. Mecha, and R. Velazco, "Inherent Uncertainty in the Determination of Multiple Event Cross Sections in Radiation Tests," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 67, no. 7, pp. 1547–1554, July 2020. doi: /10.1109/TNS.2020.2977698.
- [6] J. A. Clemente, F. J. Franco, F. Villa, M. Baylac, S. Rey, H. Mecha, J. A. Agapito, H. Puchner, G. Hubert, and R. Velazco, "Statistical Anomalies of Bitflips in SRAMs to Discriminate SBUGs From MCUs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 2087–2094, Aug. 2016. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2016.2551263.
- [7] F. J. Franco, J. A. Clemente, M. Baylac, S. Rey, F. Villa, H. Mecha, J. A. Agapito, H. Puchner, G. Hubert, and R. Velazco, "Statistical Deviations From the Theoretical Only-SBU Model to Estimate MCU Rates in SRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 64, no. 8, pp. 2152–2160, Aug. 2017. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2017.2726938.
- [8] J. Guo, G. Mao, W. Liu, C. Shao, R. Wu, Y. Li, J. Zhao, C. Shen, H. Mou, L. Zhang, H. Li, and G. Du, "The Bitmap Decryption Model on Interleaved SRAM Using Multiple-Bit Upset Analysis," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 69, no. 8, pp. 1857–1864, Aug. 2022. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2022.3186083.
- [9] M. Wirthlin, D. Lee, G. Swift, and H. Quinn, "A Method and Case Study on Identifying Physically Adjacent Multiple-Cell Upsets Using 28-nm, Interleaved and SECEDED-Protected Arrays," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 61, no. 6, pp. 3080–3087, Dec. 2014. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2014.2366913.
- [10] J. C. Fabero, H. Mecha, F. J. Franco, J. A. Clemente, G. Korkian, S. Rey, B. Cheymol, M. Baylac, G. Hubert, and R. Velazco, "Single Event Upsets Under 14-MeV Neutrons in a 28-nm SRAM-Based FPGA in Static Mode," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 67, no. 7, pp. 1461–1469, July 2020. doi: /10.1109/TNS.2020.2977874.
- [11] A. Pérez-Celis and M. J. Wirthlin, "A Statistical Method to Extract Radiation-Induced Multiple-Cell Upsets in SRAM-Based FPGAs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 50–56, Jan. 2020. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2019.2955006.
- [12] V. Vlagkoulis, A. Sari, J. Vrachnis, G. Antonopoulos, N. Segkos, M. Psarakis, A. Tavoularis, G. Furano, C. Boatella Polo, C. Poivey, V. Ferlet-Cavrois, M. Kastriotou, P. Fernandez Martinez, R. G. Alia, K.-O. Voss, and C. Schuy, "Single Event Effects Characterization of the Programmable Logic of Xilinx Zynq-7000 FPGA Using Very/Ultra High-Energy Heavy Ions," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 36–45, Jan. 2021. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2020.3033188.
- [13] S. Gao, X.-Y. Li, S.-W. Zhao, Z. He, B. Ye, L. Cai, Y.-M. Sun, G.-Q. Xiao, C. Cai, and J. Liu, "Heavy ion-induced MCUs in 28 nm SRAM-based FPGAs: upset proportions, classifications, and pattern shapes," *Nucl. Sci. Tech.*, vol. 33, no. 12, Dec. 2022. Article number 161. doi:10.1007/s41365-022-01142-7.
- [14] A. Pérez-Celis, C. Thurlow, and M. Wirthlin, "Identifying Radiation-Induced Micro-SEFIs in SRAM FPGAs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 68, no. 10, pp. 2480–2487, Oct. 2021. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2021.3108572.
- [15] L. Dilillo, G. Tsiligianis, V. Gupta, A. Bossler, F. Saigne, and F. Wrobel, "Soft errors in commercial off-the-shelf static random access memories," *Semicond. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 32, no. 1, Dec. 2016. Article number 013006. doi:10.1088/1361-6641/32/1/013006.
- [16] C. Poivey, T. Carriere, J. Beaucour, and T. Oldham, "Characterization of single hard errors (SHE) in 1 M-bit SRAMs from single ion," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 41, no. 6, pp. 2235–2239, Dec. 1994. doi:10.1109/23.340568.
- [17] R. Gaillard and G. Poirault, "Numerical simulation of hard errors induced by heavy ions in 4T high density SRAM cells," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 613–618, June 1994. doi:10.1109/23.299808.

- [18] H. Shindou, S. Kuboyama, N. Ikeda, T. Hirao, and S. Matsuda, "Bulk damage caused by single protons in SDRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 50, no. 6, pp. 1839–1845, Dec. 2003. doi:10.1109/TNS.2003.820727.
- [19] J.-P. David, F. Bezerra, E. Lorfevre, T. Nuns, and C. Inguibert, "Light Particle-Induced Single Event Degradation in SDRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 53, no. 6, pp. 3544–3549, Dec. 2006. doi:10.1109/TNS.2006.886210.
- [20] H. Shindou, S. Kuboyama, N. Ikeda, Y. Satoh, T. Hirao, and T. Tamura, "Evaluation of the Proton Induced Bulk Damage in SDRAM Utilizing 90 nm Process Technology," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 54, no. 6, pp. 2233–2237, Dec. 2007. doi:10.1109/TNS.2007.910876.
- [21] L. D. Edmonds and L. Z. Scheick, "Physical Mechanisms of Ion-Induced Stuck Bits in the Hyundai 16M × 4 SDRAM," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 55, no. 6, pp. 3265–3271, Dec. 2008. doi:10.1109/TNS.2008.2006902.
- [22] A. M. Chugg, A. J. Burnell, P. H. Duncan, S. Parker, and J. J. Ward, "The Random Telegraph Signal Behavior of Intermittently Stuck Bits in SDRAMs," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 3057–3064, Dec. 2009. doi:10.1109/TNS.2009.2032184.
- [23] R. Koga, S. Crain, K. Crawford, and P. Yu, "Heavy ion induced hard errors in memory devices with sub-micron feature sizes," in *RADECS2001. 6th European Conference on Radiation and Its Effects on Components and Systems (Cat. No.01TH8605)*, (Grenoble, France), pp. 423–430, Sept. 2001. doi:10.1109/RADECS.2001.1159317.
- [24] S. Duzellier, S. Bourdarie, R. Velazco, B. Nicolescu, and R. Ecoffet, "SEE in-flight data for two static 32KB memories on high earth orbit," in *IEEE Radiation Effects Data Workshop*, (Phoenix, USA), pp. 1–6, July 2002. doi:10.1109/REDW.2002.1045524.
- [25] J. George, R. Koga, K. Crawford, P. Yu, S. Crain, and V. Tran, "SEE sensitivity trends in non-hardened high density SRAMs with sub-micron feature sizes," in *IEEE Radiation Effects Data Workshop*, (Monterey, USA), pp. 83–88, July 2003. doi:10.1109/REDW.2003.1281350.
- [26] A. Haran, J. Barak, D. David, E. Keren, N. Refaeli, and S. Rapaport, "Single Event Hard Errors in SRAM Under Heavy Ion Irradiation," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 61, no. 5, pp. 2702–2710, Oct. 2014. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2014.2345697.
- [27] Q. Sun *et al.*, "Gate breakdown induced stuck bits in sub-20nm finfet sram," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 125, no. 2, p. 022101, July 2024. doi:10.1063/5.0214621.
- [28] J. Shao *et al.*, "Heavy ion-induced microdose effects on the reliability of planar and FinFET-based SRAM physical unclonable functions," *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, vol. 124, no. 26, p. 262103, June 2024. doi:10.1063/5.0213157.
- [29] M. Martone, M. Angelone, and M. Pillon, "The 14 MeV Frascati neutron generator," *J. Nucl. Mater.*, vol. 212215, pp. 1661–1664, Sept. 1994. doi: 10.1016/0022-3115(94)91109-6.
- [30] J. A. Clemente, M. Rezaei, J. C. Fabero, H. Mecha, and F. J. Franco, "LELAPE: An Open-Source Tool to Classify SEUs According to Their Multiplicity in Radiation-Ground Tests on Memories," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 71, no. 10, pp. 2260–2271, Aug. 2024. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2024.3450607.
- [31] J. A. Clemente, F. J. Franco, F. Villa, M. Baylac, P. Ramos, V. Vargas, H. Mecha, J. A. Agapito, and R. Velazco, "Single Events in a COTS Soft-Error Free SRAM at Low Bias Voltage Induced by 15-MeV Neutrons," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 2072–2079, Aug. 2016. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2016.2522819.
- [32] M. Rezaei, F. J. Franco, A. Colangeli, and J. A. Clemente, "Neutron-induced upsets and stuck bits on COTS pseudo-static RAMs," in *IEEE Radiation Effects Data Workshop (REDW)*, (Nashville, USA), pp. –, IEEE, July 2025. In press.
- [33] R. García-Alfá, A. Coronetti, K. Bilkó, M. Cecchetto, G. Datzmann, S. Fiore, and S. Girard, "Heavy Ion Energy Deposition and SEE Intercomparison Within the RADNEXT Irradiation Facility Network," *IEEE Trans. Nucl. Sci.*, vol. 70, no. 8, pp. 1596–1605, Aug. 2023. doi: 10.1109/TNS.2023.3260309.